

From the Office of the Director

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Welcome to the inaugural edition of *The Mirror*—the newsletter for NSF’s National Optical-Infrared Astronomy Research Laboratory (NOIRLab for short). A new organization that unifies all of NSF’s night-time ground-based observatories under a single umbrella, NOIRLab is also much more. It unifies observatories and communities to create a center that is stronger, more capable, and more diverse and inclusive than the sum of its parts. While our name reflects the central role of our primary sponsor, the US National Science Foundation, NOIRLab brings together US and international partners through Gemini, SOAR, and other initiatives, as well as inter-agency partnerships and collaborations with the US Department of Energy and NASA.

Our choice of “*The Mirror*” for the name of this newsletter series is more than a reflection on the central role of optics in our field. A mirror allows us to see ourselves as others do. As we launch NOIRLab and this newsletter series, it is important that we be aware of how you see us in

the present, understand the aspirations of our community, and engage with you as we create a shared vision for the future. In this inaugural volume, five distinguished scientists share their thoughts on the proper role of a national observatory.

While its name is new, *The Mirror* builds on the missions and traditions of its predecessors, the GeminiFocus and NOAO Newsletter series. The new newsletter series will continue to provide updates for all of the programs that comprise NOIRLab, both information of interest to a broad community and communications targeted to specific user communities (e.g., Gemini’s international partners). So you can rest assured that information critical to users, and their sponsors, will be provided in forms tailored to local needs.

As you will read in this volume, an enormous amount of activity is underway at NOIRLab. We are revitalizing the AO capabilities of Gemini North, working with our colleagues from Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory to commission the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument on the Mayall telescope, and collaborating with a team of scientists led by Penn State to bring a next-generation precision radial velocity instrument to the WIYN telescope with the support of NASA. The operations team for the Rubin Observatory is well along in developing operations plans that will drive both the time-domain and data revolutions that are underway in our field.

All of this activity and planning has, however, not escaped the current global pandemic. Our mountaintop facilities and offices in Chile and Arizona are closed temporarily as a result of COVID-19 to protect the health of our staff, their families, and local communities. Gemini North is now back online, and we look forward to getting back on the sky with the telescopes at Kitt Peak, Cerro Tololo, and Cerro Pachón when local conditions allow. Please check our websites for regular updates.

Lastly, while this is a newsletter for the NOIRLab community, the news is ultimately generated by our user community and sponsors. We would be delighted to hear from you regarding interesting science results, your opinions and aspirations, capabilities you would like to see, and suggestions for improvements in our communications. Stay in touch and, most importantly, stay safe.